

THE NAME UKRAINE AND ITS VARIABILITY IN UKRAINIAN PROSE ABOUT THE NATIONAL LIBERATION MOVEMENT OF THE FIRST HALF OF THE TWENTIETH CENTURY

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Abstract

The article presents an onomastic study of the functioning of the toponym Ukraine in the texts of twenty Ukrainian prose works about the national-liberation movement of the first half of the twentieth century. The basic scientists' researches of geographical names and influence of individuals and society on their connotative value's formation have been considered in the article. The importance of influence of social and political events, emotional-psychological experience and writers' world's perceptions have been determined on the formation of connotative-associative layers on the general-conceptual semantics of the propriative Ukraine. The quantitative uses of variants of the toponym Ukraine in the texts of twenty Ukrainian works, the motivation of the names and their structural features have been established. It has been discovered, that structurally the name Ukraine has been used by writers in the form of a 1-lexeme unit, 2 (3) – component structure and multiplex formations. The name Ukraine in the twenty Ukrainian prose works has been presented in its variants with the attributes by the writers' personal feelings, the State's territorial features, the governmental system and political regime, the colour sign of governing ideologies, the state symbols and with the attributive-personal noun mother (nanny). The associative-connotative semantics of the toponym Ukraine with its variants has been established.

Keywords: connotation, onomastics, appellative, propriative, toponym, motivation, khoronym, connotonym.

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1. Introduction

The systemic structure of the onyms within one fictive work builds a hierarchy of all propriatives, where each proper name performs a primary function – nominative, that is, it names an object, territory, state or other.

This opinion is confirmed by the Russian researcher Oleksandra Superanska, who notes that geographical names mark either the past or the present, and “have or must have a historical explanation” [1].

However, apart from the nominative function, very often the names of geographical objects take on connotative layers, new emotional-nuanced semantic colours, which have been caused by cultural, historical or other factors in society and the state in particular.

Socio-political events of a particular territory, and therefore of society, have consequently been reflected in the toponyms in the works of fiction, where writers emphasize the peculiarities of laws of that time by the auxiliary attributes.

Lyubov Mats'ko, a scientist from Ukraine, writes about a narrower understanding of connotative semantics, noting that, in fact, it is such a component of the meaning of a word that makes it possible to use it for a secondary nomination. It arises on associative-imaginative representations [2]. Confirming this, Veronica Petruliak points out that the study of connotation opens up a better understanding of “not only linguistic phenomena, but also history and culture, because the sources of connotation could be seen only in them” [3]. The linguist Yevgen Otin calls toponyms with additional semantic loading “connotative toponyms” or connotonyms [4] because of the emotional colouring that the geographical names do not have. The scientist Volodymyr Nikonov says about the indisputable connection of connotonyms and society, and consequently their reflection by writers in the texts of works of art: “Even if the names indicate the features of the object, then the selection of these features is due only to the interests of the society” [5]. Obviously, that the connotonyms in the texts of works of art with the depended characteristic attributes are transmitted through the

writers' world outlook to the recipient. Therefore, the author sees the individual approach of writers to form their own proper names, namely toponymies, through their personal-psychological experience and a style of presentation.

John Humpers notes that most people in everyday situations have considerable freedom to choose which of several role-playing relationships to take, so interactivists deny the parallel between social and physical dimensions [6]. Continuing the theme of interaction between humans as individuals and societies, the linguist Roger Bell pointed the difference between the so-called micro- and macrosociolinguistics: macrosociolinguistics focuses on the individual in the group, at the level of large groups, even at the level of nations and states that have mutual contacts [7].

A lack of research of connotation in toponyms in the works of fiction with a historical direction, the influence of individually-imaginative, psychologically-social way of thinking of broadcasters on the formation of attributive characteristics of toponyms, the variability of the khoronyms under the influence of political and ideological factors determines the relevance of the chosen topic.

The *aim* of our onomastic research is to determine the variability, functional loading and structural features of the khoronym *Ukraine* on the material of 8 Ukrainian prose works of memoirs literature about the national liberation movement of 1942–1954 and 12 novels about the national liberation movement of Ukraine 1917–1922.

2. Materials and Methods

To achieve the goal, namely to establish the quantity, variability of the name *Ukraine*, motivational explanation of its structural use with dependent attributes by the writers under the influence of social-ideological and especially psychological factors, the author has worked on 20 texts of novels and works of memoirs literature about the national liberation movement in *Ukraine* of the first half of the twentieth century. The most frequent is the toponym *Ukraine* of all the toponyms that the writers use in the analyzed texts. Obviously, the name *Ukraine* has become the center and goal of all the rebel's competitions and efforts, and, of course, cost many their own lives. *Ukraine* has been the main topic of conversations and discussions of characters in the novels for decades, and the relevant topic continues to be relevant. In general, the toponym *Ukraine* with its variability is mentioned 1,189 times in twenty texts of *Ukrainian* works, and only the one-name *Ukraine* has 1,086 units. The largest number is used by Vasyl Fol'varochnyj in the novel "Symon Petljura" (261 titles *Ukraine*), and the least number uses Roman Ivanychuk in the parable "The fiery columns" (3 units). In fact, in the remaining 18 texts, the situation with the functioning of the toponym *Ukraine* (without variants of the name) is: "The flame from the Cold Ravine" (22 names), "Jerusalem is on the mountains" (135 names), "And they were first to die" (47 names), "Marus'a" (10 titles), "We'll be back!" (142 titles), "The Moroziv's Farmstead" (38 titles), "On the foreign winds" (17 titles), "The stick for lepers" (22 titles), "The early Deer's Roar" (21 titles), "On the pathways of the Cold Ravine" (64 titles), "The case of the chieftain Zelenyj" (13 titles), "In the eternal whirlpool" (22 titles), "In the steppes of Kherson" (24 titles), "The Cold Ravine" (111 titles), "Red" (15 titles), "What doesn't the fire heal" (45 titles), "The one who stayed" (15 titles), "With the strong waves of the wings" (59 titles).

The author worked on the 20 texts of *Ukrainian* prose about the national-liberation movement of the first half of the twentieth century. In general, the toponym *Ukraine* with its variability is mentioned 1,189 times in twenty texts of *Ukrainian* works, and only the one-name *Ukraine* has 1,086 units. It also was focused on the difference of usage of the name *Ukraine* in the 15 fiction works and 5 texts of the victim's memoirs (Table 1).

Table 1

The total number of use of the name *Ukraine*; the difference in usage between novels and memoirs

Number of uses of the name	Name <i>Ukraine</i>
The total number of uses of the name <i>Ukraine</i> with its variants	1189
The number of uses of the one-word variant of the name <i>Ukraine</i>	1086
The number of uses of the name <i>Ukraine</i> in the 15 fiction works	700
The number of uses of the name <i>Ukraine</i> in the 5 memoirs texts	386

The author formed the variability of eight names of the *Ukrainian* state in the texts of 20 *Ukrainian* prose works, in which the writers show their own attitude, feelings and the social-political influence (**Table 2**).

Table 2

A quantitative use of eight variants of the name *Ukraine* in the texts of the 20 analyzed works

Names	Ukraine	State	Motherland	Region	Vkraina (phonetical variant of Ukraine U/V)	Land	Nanny	Homeland
A quantitative use of variants of the name <i>Ukraine</i>	1086	54	30	7	4	3	3	2
Total %	78,4 %	4,5 %	2,7 %	0,6 %	0,4 %	0,3 %	0,3 %	0,2 %

Note: the analysis was conducted on the basis of the texts of the 20 works about the national liberation movement in **Ukraine** the first half of the twentieth century (15 novels and 5 texts-memoirs)

3. Results

Structurally, the name *Ukraine* is used by writers in the form of a 1-lexeme unit, 2 (3) – component structure and multiplex formations.

1. 1. Among the **one-lexeme variants**, the authors of the texts refer to the word *Ukraine* as *State* (28 titles). In fact, the writers point the general name *State* in the capital letter, referring to the name *Ukraine*, and since almost all the efforts in the years of the first decades of the twentieth century were aimed at gaining statehood in *Ukraine*, the name *State* received somewhat sacred meaning for Ukrainians: “Every authority that took the helm of *State* had to negotiate with this fair requirement of the peasants” [8]. The third most frequent mention (after *Ukraine* and *State*), namely 27 units, in the texts of the analyzed works is the name **Motherland**, which equally replaces the name *Ukraine*: “... teachers at school are afraid to say the word “Ukraine” out loud to students, they must add “Soviet” to *Ukraine*, or substitute *Ukraine* for “Homeland”, “Motherland”, and they are also monitored by unclean power from the party hell ...” [9, 10]. Similarly in the six texts of the works there are also the following concepts and variants of the names *Ukraine*: **Homeland** [11], **Vkraina** (phonetical variant of *Ukraine U/V*) [12, 13], **Land** (**Big Land** [14], **Ukrainian Land** [12], **Native Land** [11]), **Region** [15], [16] (**Native Region** [11]), **Nanny** [17].

1. 2. **Two- (three) – component structures** that occur in the texts of the analyzed works, can be semantically divided into sub-structural types, namely:

1. 2. 1. Name **Ukraine/Motherland/Homeland/Region/Nanny** with adjectives, denoting **personal feelings**: perhaps, taking into consideration the tragedy of Ukrainian history, especially in the first half of the twentieth century, the authors of the analyzed texts use variants (11) of the names of *Ukraine* with characteristic adjectives of negative semantics, sometimes with a gradational increase, for example: **talentless, unfortunate Ukraine** [8], **poor-poor mother Ukraine** [8], **dear Homeland** [12], **miserable Ukraine** [8, 12], **unfortunate Region** [11], **our wretched Motherland** [8], **unhappy Ukraine** [17], **unhappy Nanny** [17], **forced Ukraine** [18], **captive Motherland** [18], **humiliated Ukraine** [9], **favourite motherland Ukraine** [18]. Antin Krushelnytskyj is the only writer, who uses positive characterizing adjectives with the toponym *Ukraine*: “Colonel Topir welcomes the chieftain as the first swallow from free *Ukraine*, from that **charming, fairy-tale Ukraine** ...” [13].

1. 2. 2. Name **Ukraine/State/Motherland/Nanny** with adjectives, denoting **territorial features**: the highest frequency (41 units) is inherent in the texts to the two-lexeme variant **Big Ukraine** (where the characterizing adjective **Big** is also fixed as a part of its proper name from the capital letter), the meaning of which does not originate from the primary semantics of the adjective. Using 41 times a connection **Big Ukraine**, the writers were referring to the lands, located along the Zbruch River – Naddniprianshchyna, Slobozhanshchyna. For example, in Olga Yavorska’s text it can be read: “Some of them even went to town for a rally, which was conducted to the **honour of the liberation and reunification of Western Ukrainian lands with Big Ukraine**” [19]. Roman Fedorov also gives his explanation: “We crossed Zbruch, such a river is in Podillya, and occurred in

Big Ukraine” [20]. In the work “In the eternal whirlpool” the author Volodymyr Lopuschanskyj used the two-lexeme substitute for *Western Ukraine – Halyska Nanny*, putting into this connection certain personal preferences: “We layed down with the chest, mouth: – *Halyska Nanny, hug us to your warm womb!*” [17].

Pointing the lands of Western Ukraine, writer Antin Krushelnytskyj introduces the two-lexeme unit of Galician Ukraine into the structure of toponymic names, and contrasts it with steppe Ukraine, referring to people, who fought for independence in different territories of the state: “...colonel *Topir congratulates with a short speech the bold persons, brave sons of steppe Ukraine, who have just freed themselves and do not forget their sister of Galician Ukraine*” [13]. The author of this article uses the different two-lexeme structures about 17 times in the texts of the works, which are noting the territorial parts of *Ukraine*, for example: *Carpathian Ukraine*: “*You are a man much younger and you may not remember that in the early spring the Carpathian Ukraine fell*” [9, 10], *the Southern Ukraine* [16], *the Right-Bank Ukraine* [8, 11], *the East Ukraine* [19], *the Central Ukraine* [10].

1. 2. 3. Name *Ukraine/State/Motherland* with adjectives, denoting *the governmental system, the political regime*: in addition to the analyzed variants, there are 18 two-lexeme variants with a clarification of the toponymic adjective *Ukrainian*. The writers' use of the two lexemes *Ukrainian State* with the capital letter is very important, so that they are emphasizing on the importance of *Ukraine's* existence and gaining independence in the struggle: “We must make them agree that Soviet Ukraine is a *Ukrainian State*” [10, 21]. The author includes into this group four three-lexeme structures with the name *State*, where the writers focus on the adjective *independent*: “... to the *Kholodnyy Yar, which will be appreciated and recognized by the future generations with the cradle, where the unprecedented power of struggle for the Ukrainian Independent State was born ...*” [11, 21].

In the other five three-lexeme and multilexemes compounds with the name *State*, the author uses such adjectives as *free, independent, self-dependent, cathedral, sovereign*, for example: *free, independent, cathedral and sovereign Ukrainian state!* [22], *Free Ukrainian State* [11], *Independent separate State* [11], *Cathedral and Independent Ukrainian State* [8], *Ukrainian Independent State* [19].

There is a very determining use of a two-lexeme compound *Free Motherland* by Yuriy Gorlis-Gorskyj (in the texts-memoirs both are indicated by the capital letters), which outlines the desire and purpose of the writer in the fight: “– *When I die and you will be alive, send greetings to your comrades, to all, who are struggling and who are still struggling. Once upon a time in the Free Motherland, I will also be remembered with a kind word*” [10]. Eighteen uses in the texts have the two-lexeme unit *Soviet Ukraine*: “We have a *Soviet Ukraine, isn't it? Which Ukraine do we need more?*” [9, 10]. Also semantically related to *Soviet Ukraine* are the connections *Bilshovyk Ukraine*: “– *Are we really going to have to build Bilshovyk Ukraine?*” [23] and *Undersoviet Ukraine*: “*Undersoviet Ukraine is worse than Poland*” [19]. The semantically different is the conjunction *Independent Ukraine* in the texts, which is embodied in 16 cases, for example: “*These leaders were treating the population with great indignation, because the village did not support them, but gave their votes for Independent Ukraine*” [8, 9]. Equal to *Independent Ukraine* is the expression *Free Ukraine*, which is mentioned in 14 cases, such as: “*Who will live up to Free Ukraine, greet her from me*” [15, 16]. In this way the author also semantically refers a two-lexeme participle *liberated Ukraine*: “... some will already die, others will go to work peacefully and the *liberated Ukraine will not even know the names of its knights*” [24] and a multi-component structure with a phonetic version of *free* (*vil'na/vol'na*): “– *May Ukraine live in a long, free, united, independent way! – cried the chieftain*” [17].

The toponymic unit *Western Ukraine* has a particular emphasis by authors in the six texts of the works, who outline a number of *Ukrainian lands*. Thus, the two-lexeme name of *Ukraine*, which covers the western lands of the country, writers mention fourteen times: “It is almost since our Germans have been expelled from *Western Ukraine by re-establishing their power here*” [8, 14]. In the text-memoirs of Stepan Semenyuk there is a three-lexeme structure with the characteristic adjective: *Free Western Ukraine*: “In 1939, before the elections to the so-called Public Assembly, someone called out to us: “Long live *Free Western Ukraine ...*” [21].

The question of the integrity and unity of *Ukraine* and Ukrainians has always been relevant. That is why in four texts the writers emphasize this, using characterizing adjectives such as: *reunited Ukraine* [9], *united Ukraine* [17], *cathedral Ukraine* [8, 17], *all-in-one, united Ukraine* [12], *whole Ukraine* [9]. The hope in the independence of Ukraine was sometimes lost, despite all efforts and actions, so that *Ukraine* is not called otherwise, but a *dreamy, mythical Ukraine* [22], *some Ukraine*: “Suddenly, someone will notice that I am wandering between graves of Sich Riflemen, who wanted *some Ukraine*” [9]. Generally, Ukraine is named in the following variants: *autonomous Ukraine* [12], *democratic Ukraine* [12], *princely Ukraine* [16], *the future independent Ukraine* [22], *the newly-emerged state Ukraine* [12], *the independent Ukraine* [8, 10], *the independent free Ukraine* [8], *Ukrainian Ukraine* [10], *the extensive Ukraine* [17]. And Roman Ivanychuk calls the process of gaining independence, autonomy, freedom, and catholicity *the Way of Freedom* in the parable “The fiery columns”. A special is the use of both lexemes in the capital letters, which symbolize the Ukrainian rebels and their struggle: “Oh, the uneasy footprint of this road crossed the river across our land! And we went out to the battle to lay *the Way of Freedom*” [23].

1. 2. 4. *Name Ukraine with adjectives denoting the colour sign of governing ideologies and state symbols*: considering the amount of Ukraine’s captive lands and the party ideology that has been conducted, the writer Roman Fedorov emphasizes different parts of the state with diverse people through the characteristic colour adjectives that symbolize either *Soviet Ukraine* or *Ukrainian*, for example: “blue-yellow” Ukraine : “They hated each other so much: your *Zenyk supports red Ukraine and my boys encourage blue and yellow Ukraine*” [9], *red Ukraine* [9], *happy red Ukraine*: “The enemy covered the land with betrayal, bribery, promises *some lucky red Ukraine and... oh we must fight against it. Because red Ukraine is a bloodied land*” [9].

1. 2. 5. *Name Ukraine/Nanny with attributive-personal noun mother (nanny)*: the personification of Ukraine as a second mother is quite common and familiar to the Ukrainian characters of the analyzed works. For the sake of *Mother-Ukraine*, the rebels left their homes with their mothers and went to the war. Therefore, the use of the author’s *Nanny-Ukraine* and *Mother-Ukraine* are both symbolic and traditional, for example: *nanny Ukraine* [9], *Nanny Ukraine* [25], “nanny-Ukraine” [26], *free nanny Ukraine* [15]; *Mother-Ukraine* [8, 18], *mother Ukraine* [10, 16], *affectionate Mother-Ukraine*: “The forest and the field around them have laid their native bed for their *affectionate MOTHER-UKRAINE*” [8].

4. Discussion

Summarizing the conducted research, the author considers that it is necessary to note that the analysis of the name *Ukraine* and its variants was carried out on the basis of 20 texts about the national liberation movement for independence of Ukraine. In its turn, the texts are numerically rich not only in anthroponymic names, but also in toponyms, because the writers did the disposition of territorial battles, competitions and contests of historical events in particular. So, there are around 2006 names of toponyms, denoting different territorial units: villages, towns, cities, rivers, mountains and lakes. The analyzed periods are quantitatively different from each other: so, the toponyms in the works that present 1917–1924 years are numerically larger, namely 1295 units, than the toponyms of the works of 1942–1954 years, which have 711 titles. The author underlines that among the all toponyms, the name *Ukraine* with its variants is the central core, the landmark, the purpose of all events and, ultimately, the most used toponym in the texts. A profound quantitative calculation of the writers’ use of the toponym *Ukraine* has been made in the texts of 20 works, which revealed 1086 single-lexeme uses of the toponym (78.4 %), from which 700 names occur in the texts of the novels, and 386 units in the texts-memoirs of the witnesses of the liberation events. In addition to the toponym *Ukraine*, there are seven other possible names for the name of a country, for instance: *State* (54 names, 4.5 %), *Motherland* (30 names, 2.7 %), *Region* (7 names, 0.6 %), *Vkraina (phonetical variant)* (4 names, 0.4 %), *Earth* (3 names, 0.3 %), *Nanny* (3 names, 0.3 %), *Homeland* (2 names, 0.2 %). The writers emphasize the personal anxious feelings about Ukraine’s independence, territorial features, political regimes of the country due to their characteristic adjectives and noun attributes.

5. Conclusions

The results of the research defined that the name *Ukraine* has also 7 variants (*State, Motherland, Region, Vkraina, Earth, Nanny, Homeland*) in the texts of 20 *Ukrainian* prose works; the most used is a one-lexeme version *Ukraine* that has illustrations in the 1086 uses of total 1189 units. The writers also pointed the two- (three) component structures and multilexemes compounds with the names that present the *Ukrainian* state with their characteristic adjectives and noun attributes, for example: *united Ukraine, affectionate Mother-Ukraine*. To put the emphasis on the connection between the toponyms and the writers' world's perception, the analyzed compounds are presented by the text's authors with the attributes, which show the writers' personal feelings (*unfortunate Region*), the *State's* territorial features (*the Southern Ukraine*), the governmental system and political regime (*Soviet Ukraine*), the colour sign of governing ideologies and the state symbols (*red Ukraine*), with the attributive-personal noun mother (nanny) (*nanny Ukraine*). Due to the personal-psychological features of the writers' way of thinking and their outlook, the influence of the social environment on the formation of the semantic circle of the toponym *Ukraine* and its seven variants have been shown in the 20 analyzed texts. The following scientific researches of Ukrainian toponymics and the fact of their social connotation are considered still important and relevant.

References

- [1] Superanskaia, A. V. (1990). *Imia cherez veka i strany*. Moscow: Nauka, 192.
- [2] Matsko, L. I., Sydorenko, O. M., Matsko, O. M.; Matsko, L. I. (Ed.) (2003). *Stylistyka ukrainskoi movy*. Kyiv : Vyshcha shkola, 462.
- [3] Petruliak, V. (2007). Do pytannia pro funktsionuvannia konotatyvnykh toponimiv (na materialy zakarpatskykh mikrotoponimiv basynu r. Uzha). *Kultura narodov Prychernomorja*, 2 (110), 95–97.
- [4] Otin, Ye. S. (2005). Konoativna onomastichna leksika. *Trudy po iazykoznaniiu*. Doneck: OOO "Iugo-Vostok, LTD", 111–122.
- [5] Sukhomlyn, I. D. (1970). *Ukrainski prizvyska liudei yak vlasni rodovi nazvy*. *Hovory i onomastyka Naddnyprianshchyny*. Dnipropetrovsk: Vyd-vo Dnipropetr. derzh. universytetu, 30–58.
- [6] Gumperz, J. (1972). *Directions in sociolinguistics*. Holt, Rinehart, and Winston, 583.
- [7] Bell, R. T. (1980). *Sociolinguistika*. Moscow: Mezhdunarodnye otnosheniia, 320.
- [8] Doroshenko, M. (2015). *Stezhkamy Kholodnoiariskymy: spohady 1918–1923 rokiv*. Kyiv: FOP Stebeliak, 352.
- [9] Fedoriv, R. (2008). *Yerusalym na horakh*. Kyiv: Vyd-vo humanit. 1-ry, 608.
- [10] Horlis-Horskyi, Yu.; Koval, R. M. (Ed.) (2012). *My shche povernemos!: Spohady. Povist. Poezii. Dokumenty. Lystuvannia*. Kyiv: Istorychnyi Klub "Kholodnyi Yar"; Vinnitsya: DP "Derzhavna kartohrafichna fabryka", 432.
- [11] Stepovii, Iu. (1947). *U khersonskikh stepakh*. Munich: Kultura, 127.
- [12] Folvarochinii, V. (2010). *Simon Petliura. Kniga 3. Na probudzenomu vulkani*. Ternopil: Dzhura, 324.
- [13] Krushelnytskyi, A. (1992). *Duzhym pomakhom kryl*. Lviv: Chervona Kalyna, 225.
- [14] Kokotiukha, A. (2015). *Chervonyi*. Kharkiv: Knyzhkovyi klub "Klub Simeinoho dozvillia", 320.
- [15] Shkliar, V. (2014). *Marusia*. Kharkiv: Knyzhkovyi Klub "Klub Simeinoho Dozvillia", 320.
- [16] Shkliar, V. (2010). *Zalyshenets*. Kharkiv: Knyzhkovyi Klub "Klub Simeinoho Dozvillia", 384.
- [17] Lopushchanskyi, V. (1992). *U spokonvichnomu vyri*. Lviv: Chervona Kalyna, 378.
- [18] Liutyi-Liutenko, I. (2015). *Vohon z Kholodnoho Yaru*. Kyiv: FOP Stebeliak, 352.
- [19] Yavorska, O. (2015). *Na chuzhykh vitrakh*. Lviv: Apriori, 260.
- [20] Fedoriv, R. (2000). *Palytsia dlia prokazhenykh*. Lviv: "Chervona Kalyna", 424.
- [21] Semeniuk, S. (2010). *I hynuly pershymy. Notatky volynskoho pidpilnyka*. Lutsk: VMA "Teren", 228.
- [22] Samchuk, U. (2008). *Choho ne hoit ohon*. Kyiv: MAUP, 352.
- [23] Ivanychuk, R. (2009). *Vohnenni stovpy: Tetralohiia*. Kharkiv: Folio, 507.
- [24] Horlis-Horskyi, Yu.; Koval, R. (Ed.) (2010). *Kholodnyi Yar: spohady osavula 1-ho kurenia polku haidamakiv Kholodnoho Yaru*. Kyiv: Istorychnyi klub "Kholodnyi Yar"; Vinnitsya: DP "Derzhavna kartohrafichna fabryka", 512.
- [25] Kokotiukha, A. (2014). *Sprava otamana Zelenoho. Ukrainski khroniky 1919 roku*. Kharkiv: Knyzhkovyi Klub "Klub Simeinoho Dozvillia", 304.
- [26] Samchuk, U. (2005). *OST. Moroziv khutir. Vol. 1. Ternopil: Dzhura, 452.*

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